

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Derivatives of Thiopyrazolone and Their Oxidation Products

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Manuscript received 17 May 1982, revised 2 April 1983, accepted 20 May 1983

On treatment with P_2S_5 , pyrazolone affords thiopyrazolone which on condensation with 4-monobromo- and 4-dibromopyrazolones in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratio, respectively yield mixed *bis* and *tris* derivatives. The *bis* compounds of thiopyrazolone are also prepared from thiopyrazolone. All these compounds with their oxidised derivatives have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, m.p. and ir spectral data. They are also assayed for their antifungal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. The unsaturated product retards the fungitoxicity. Some of the compounds show a very good fungicidal activity and are compared with standard commercial fungicides.

IN continuation of our work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁶, it has been observed that 5-pyrazolones possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae*. Further, replacement of carbonyl oxygen by sulphur enhances the fungicidal activity markedly⁴ and 4-nitroso pyrazolone and 4,4'-*bis*-pyrazolones exhibit significant fungicidal activity¹⁻⁵. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to study the fungitoxicity of 4,4'-*bis*-thiopyrazolones.

Thiopyrazolones were obtained from pyrazolone on treatment with P_2S_5 in xylene. Thiopyrazolone (I), condensed with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (II) in 1 : 1 proportion and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-dibromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VII) in 2 : 1 proportion in presence of ethanol and fused sodium acetate yields 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (III) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-(1''-phenyl-3''-methyl-2''-pyrazolin-5''-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VIII), respectively. The structure of III was established from elemental analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The ir spectra of III show the characteristic $>C=O$ group absorption band at 1600 cm^{-1} , $>C-CH_3$ group stretching vibration band at 1400 cm^{-1} and the broad band in between 2200 to 2900 cm^{-1} attributed to $>C-SH$ stretching vibration. The nmr data show that a multiplet at $\delta 7.32$ is due to the 10 protons of the two phenyl groups. A singlet appearing at $\delta 6.25$ is assigned to the two protons of the adjacent methine groups in [a, e] configuration. Methine groups in [ee/aa] configuration also gave a doublet at $\delta 3.77$. A multiplet appearing at $\delta 2.1$ is for the protons of $>C-CH_3$ group attached to the pyrazolone nucleus. The peak at $\delta 0.9$ is attributed to the three protons of the methyl group of the thiopyrazolone ring.

The molecular ion peak of this compound occurs at 362 m/e. The fragmentation pattern is shown below.

m/e=362
a=77 for Ph gr.=f
b=106 for Ph-N=N=e
c=28 for C=O
d=33 for SH.

The structure of VIII was established from elemental analysis and ir data. The ir spectral data show the presence of bands at 1480 , 1590 and 1055 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the stretching vibration of $>C-CH_3$, $>C=O$ and $>C=S$, respectively. The broad band in between 2200 - 2900 cm^{-1} is due to $>C-SH$ group.

The structures of the oxidation products (IV) and (IX), obtained by standard procedure from III and VIII, were established from their elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir spectra show the absence of bands due to $-SH$ group.

Treated with phenyl hydrazine, I gives rise to 4,4'-*bis* derivative of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (X). The structure was established from elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir data show the presence of bands at 1052 and 1460 cm^{-1} due to $>C=S$ and $>C-CH_3$ group stretching vibrations, respectively as also the broad band in between 2200 - 2900 cm^{-1} due to $>C-SH$ group.

The structure of the oxidation product XI obtained from X as per standard method was established from elemental analysis and ir spectra. The

spectra show the absence of band due to -SH group.

Condensed with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (V) in presence of ethanol and fused sodium acetate, II gives rise to 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-4'-nitroso-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VI). The structure was established from elemental analysis and ir data. The ir absorption bands at 1590 and 1250 cm^{-1} are ascribed to C=O and C=S stretching vibrations, respectively. Bands at 700 and 680 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the aromatic ring.

All the compounds prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* by using the spore germination tests at various concentrations by the standard method⁷. It is observed that compounds III, IIIa, IV, VI, VIII and X (Table 1), with R=Ph, exhibited pronounced antifungal activity against these two pathogens. Maximum fungitoxicity (100%) was recorded by III against *P. oryzae* and by VIII (with R=Ph) against *H. oryzae* (98%) at 1000 ppm. The compound (X) and the nitroso derivative (VI) inhibited 95% of spore germination of both the

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Compound	R	m.p. °C	sulphur % Found (Calcd.)	% inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
					<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	III	Ph	184	8.20 (8.88)	100	75
2.	IIIa	H	300	10.95 (11.18)	65	60
3.	IV	Ph	105	9.25 (8.85)	75	60
4.	IVa	H	120	10.85 (11.26)	53	49
5.	VI	Ph	125	8.39 (8.16)	95	95
6.	VIa	H	195	10.65 (10.12)	73	78
7.	VIII	Ph	192	10.12 (11.63)	88	93
8.	IX	Ph	285	10.98 (11.67)	63	75
9.	X	Ph	160	15.48 (16.93)	95	80
10.	XI	Ph	135	17.81 (17.02)	63	75

pathogens at 1000 ppm concentration. In general the oxidation product IX and XI showed ~65%

spore germination inhibition against both the pathogens at 1000 ppm concentration.

It is concluded from these results that the C₄-nitroso, *bis* and *tris* derivatives of the mixed 5-thio-pyrazolones showed higher fungitoxicity than that of the parent compound. The creation of the double bond at C₄₋₄, position retards the activity.

Some standard fungicides like *o*-ethyl-S-S-diphenyl phosphorodithionate (Hinosan 50%) EC, difolatan 50% WP and derosal 60% WP, which show respectively 95, 98 and 87% inhibition of spore germination of *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm were used as standards for purposes of comparison. It was observed from the activity against *P. oryzae* that the compounds III, VI, VIII, IX and X compare favourably with the standards and hence they may be tried as commercial fungicides.

Experimental

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (III) : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-monobromo-5-one (0.01 mole), 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) and fused sodium acetate (6.0 g) were taken in ethanol (25 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 4 hr over a water bath. The excess alcohol was boiled off and cooled. Ice cold water was added to it and kept overnight. White coloured compound precipitated out which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 70%.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Oxidation product of III : III (2.0 g) was taken in 10% NaOH solution and a saturated solution of I₂/KI was added to it dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 2 hr. The brown coloured compound obtained was filtered and repeatedly washed with sodium thiosulphate solution. The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous NaOH solution and gives no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-4'-nitroso-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VI) : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) were condensed together in presence of ethanol (25 ml) and fused sodium acetate (6.0 g) and ice cooled water were added to it. The white coloured compound thus obtained was crystallised from ethanol, yield 70%.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous NaOH solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione) (1''-phenyl-3''-methyl-2''-pyrazolin-5''-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (VIII) : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.02 mole), 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-dibromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) and fused sodium acetate (6.0 g) were taken in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed for 4 hr. After cooling, ice cold water was added to it. White coloured compound thus obtained was crystallised from ethanol, yield 65%.

The compound is soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Oxidation product of VIII : VIII (2.0 g) was taken in 10% aqueous NaOH solution and a saturated solution of I₂/KI was added to it dropwise with constant stirring for 2 hr. Black coloured compound thus obtained was filtered and repeatedly washed with sodium thiosulphate solution. The compound was crystallised from ethanol, yield 50%.

The compound is not soluble in 10% aqueous NaOH solution nor does it give colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-yl-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione)-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (X) : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) and phenyl hydrazine (1.0 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. The gummy mass thus obtained was cooled and dissolved in 10% aqueous alkali solution, filtered and the clear solution acidified with dil. HCl. The black coloured compound thus formed was filtered and washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 60%.

The compound is soluble in 10% aqueous NaOH solution and gives colouration with FeCl₃ solution.

Oxidation product of X : X (2.0 g) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and saturated solution of I₂/KI (25 ml) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring for 2 hr. The brown coloured compound thus obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, yield 40%.

The compound gives no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution and is not soluble in aqueous NaOH solution.

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